

A SYSTEM FOR GEOSPATIAL QUESTION-ANSWERING USING LLMs, LANGCHAIN, CHROMADB, AND A MODERN REACT.JS FRONTEND

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Abstract

The increasing demand for accurate geospatial data requires efficient data retrieval methods to help users find the data they need. This university project presents a solution that combines the power of Large Language Models (LLMs) with geospatial data from Google Maps and OpenStreetMap. The system's basic idea is to enable users to ask specific questions about locations and points of interest, providing accurate and contextually relevant responses. The system integrates LLMs, LangChain, ChromaDB, and modern frontend technologies to create an interactive map-based interface. The contribution lies in the development of a comprehensive system that leverages LLMs to generate meaningful answers and facilitates efficient retrieval of geospatial information. The system focuses on enhancing the user experience and improving the efficiency of accessing geospatial data. Future work includes expanding data sources and addressing limitations such as input quality and hallucinations in LLMs.

INTRODUCTION

Geospatial information is very important in various fields such as navigation systems, automotive or urban planning. The rapid rise in availability of digital cartography and geolocated services has escalated the demand for systems that offer both efficient interaction and ease of access to geospatial data. Conventional search tools and map-based applications often oblige users to manually sift through a voluminous amount of information to unearth specific responses to their geospatial inquiries. This method can prove to be laborious and ineffective, particularly when addressing intricate or locale-specific queries.

The main contribution of this project is the development of a geospatial question and answer system that integrates LLMs, LangChain, ChromaDB, and modern frontend technologies. The system provides an intuitive user interface where users can input search terms and receive interactive map-based results. The LLMs process the user queries and generate contextually appropriate responses using the crawled geospatial information from Google Maps and OpenStreetMap. The LangChain library facilitates the passing of pre-processed geospatial data to the LLMs, enabling them to generate meaningful and accurate answers. The ChromaDB vector store efficiently stores and retrieves the geospatial embeddings used by the LLMs, improving the overall performance of the system.

Structure

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows:

Architecture is devoted to a high level architectural overview of the entire project.

Backend provides an overview of the backend components, including Python, Flask, and data retrieval from Google Maps and OpenStreetMap.

Data retrieval explains how to crawl and retrieve the underlying data used in this project.

LangChain and Chroma explains the usage of LangChain and ChromaDB to process and store geospatial data for LLMs.

Frontend focuses on the frontend components, including React, Tailwind CSS, and Mapbox, and how they provide an interactive map interface for the system.

Conclusion This chapter concludes the paper, summarizing the key findings and contributions of the project as well as limitations and promising future work.

ARCHITECTURE

This university project attempts to develop a geospatial question and answer system. The user can input search terms into a search bar and the results are shown in an interactive map, where the question is answered by a Large Language Model (LLM) that uses crawled geospatial information from Google Maps and OpenStreetMap. The architecture is defined by a combination of LLMs, LangChain [1], ChromaDB [2], and modern frontend technologies such as React [3], Vite [4], and TailwindCSS [5]. The framework integrates a frontend, including a world map rendered using the Mapbox JS [6] library, and a backend built to retrieve, process, and interpret data to answer user queries. LangChain, a young library designed to power applications using LLMs, is used to pass pre-processed geospatial data to an LLM, enabling the model to generate meaningful and contextually appropriate responses from user questions. The following figure gives a concise overview of the entire software architecture and highlights the key components and libraries used throughout.

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Figure 1: Software architecture of the entire project.

BACKEND

Python [7] is a programming language that is commonly used for backend application development. Its easy syntax, large community and rich set of libraries make it a popular choice for all kinds of data science projects.

Flask [8] is a web framework for Python used to build web applications via REST API. For a question-answering system like the one described in this paper, Flask is used to setup a REST API that bridges frontend and backend. When a user submits a search request on the UI, Flask handles the request and calls the functions for processing this input. When processing is complete, Flask sends the response back to the UI for visualization.

Poetry [9] is a Python packaging and dependency management tool. It manages a project's dependencies by using a toml and lock file to ensure that the application will behave the same in different environments, increasing the reproducibility of the results.

The core functionality of the backend is the retrieval of the crawled data from online geospatial data providers. Furthermore, LangChains and ChromDB is used to implement the question-answering system. These concepts are explained in the following sections.

Data Retrieval

The python backend is used for data retrieval and processing of user inputs coming from the UI. The data is coming from two sources: Google Maps [10] and OpenStreetMap [11]. Google Maps data extraction is performed by Apify [12], a cloud-based web scraping tool. Apify is a scraping platform that can be used to extract website data from various sources. It allows to deploy and execute a wide range of so-called "actors" to crawl web-pages. Crawling Google Maps Places with Apify involves using the Google Places actor, a tool designed specifically for this task. The Google Maps scraper actor works by interacting with the Google Maps API to extract detailed information about places stored in Google Maps, including names, addresses, ratings, reviews, and more. The actor can be setup on the Apify platform to parameterize the crawling. During setup, parameters are provided such as the bounding box, region or city that the actor should crawl and the type of data to extract. It then sends requests to the Google Maps API to aggregate the requested information. The extracted data is then structured and stored in a dataset on the platform where it can be accessed and downloaded in various formats such as CSV or JSON. In the case of this application, Apify was used to query the Google Maps data for repair shops in Styria.

Open Street Map is a community driven mapping project where members contribute and maintain the data. All map data is freely available under an open license, making OSM a rich source of geospatial data for a variety of applications. One way to access and extract data from OSM is to use the Overpass API [13]. The Overpass API is used to extract OSM map data and export it to a suitable format such as JSON for further processing. Overpass has its own query language used to retrieve and collect information from OSM. To extract geospatial information about places and points of interest within a given bounding box, one can write an Overpass query that specifies the types of POIs that should be included in the response and the geographic area defined by a bounding box. It then returns the map data that matches the query parameters. This principle was used to retrieve all the information about repair stores in Styria for this application. The data returned includes detailed geospatial information about the matching places and POIs, such as their coordinates, names, types and other tagged information that was added to the OSM database by its contributors. Furthermore, a web crawler was implemented to additionally crawl the website data of all extracted locations. However, since Apify already provides rich information such as phone numbers, addresses and location information, there was no significant benefit to this extraction. But still, the raw crawled data can be downloaded from the UI if the user wants to explore it further.

LangChain and ChromaDB

After extraction, the raw data is processed in the Python backend to remove unnecessary content and prepare the geospatial data for use with LangChain. The next step is to convert the raw geospatial data into interpretable embeddings for LLMs. Large Language Models (LLMs) have the ability to process and generate text based on the patterns they learn from their training data. However, by their very nature, LLMs aren't designed to work directly with raw textual data, such as geospatial data, which presents a challenge when using these models in applications that require understanding such formats. This is where vector databases with embeddings come into play. Embeddings are a way of representing the data in a format that LLMs can work with effectively. These representations, often in the form of high-dimensional vectors, can capture the essential features of the original data in a format that LLMs can process. In this way, data can be stored and retrieved efficiently by LLMs. For example, when responding to a geospatial query, the system can efficiently retrieve the relevant data from the vector database, and then feed it to the LLM to generate an appropriate response that fits well into the context of the question. The embeddings are stored in ChromaDB. It is a tool that provides a performant vector store that can be easily combined with LangChain, making it ideal for creating LLM based applications [14].

FRONTEND

The front end of the system is built using React and styled with TailwindCSS. It displays an interactive map interface powered by the Mapbox library. The map displays markers representing data points, where the level of detail of each marker depends on the data source used, which can be either Google Maps or OpenStreetMaps. The front-end encourages user interaction, allowing them to click on markers to view detailed information about the given location.

React

React is a popular open source JavaScript library used to build user interfaces or UI components. Developed and maintained by Facebook, React allows developers to create large web applications that can efficiently update and render in response to data changes without requiring a full page reload. The library achieves this by introducing a virtual DOM, which is a lightweight copy of the real DOM. The virtual DOM allows React to determine which components need to be changed when an application's state changes, and then update only those components in the real DOM. Another key advantage of React is its component-based architecture. This means that one can build encapsulated components that manage their own state and then assemble them into complex user interfaces. Components are reusable, which makes development more efficient and the codebase easier to manage.

Tailwind CSS

Tailwind CSS is a CSS framework that allows developers to construct UI designs directly in their markup. Unlike traditional CSS frameworks that provide components directly, Tailwind CSS provides low-level classes that enable the construction of custom designs with ease. The architecture promotes allows reusability of components to enable rapid development. To integrate Tailwind CSS into a React.js project, one typically configures it as part of one's project's build process. Tools like Create React App or Vite have plugins that make it easy to set up Tailwind CSS. Once set up, one can use Tailwind's utility classes directly in the React components. For example, one can control the layout, typography, colors, and responsiveness of the components by adding Tailwind CSS classes to the elements in the JSX markup.

MAPBOX

Mapbox is a powerful, flexible mapping platform and geospatial services provider. It provides developers with tools to integrate location-based services, such as maps, geocoding, navigation and more, in an efficient way into their applications. In this application mapbox was used to place markers on the map for the crawled locations and color them according to the search results. The user can move around and click on the marker to get further information about the specific point.

Figure 2: Visual interface of the application

CONCLUSION, FUTURE WORK & LIMITATIONS

Overall, this project demonstrates the potential of integrating LLMs, LangChain, ChromaDB, and modern front-end technologies as a valuable proof-of-concept for a geospatial question-answering system. With further improvements, this system could have applications in various domains.

While this system is operational and able to respond to inquiries in a user-friendly manner, certain constraints exist. Primarily, the efficacy of the system is heavily influenced by the precision and clarity of user commands; incorrect or nebulous inputs could yield incorrect or potentially misleading outputs. Moreover, the challenge of system-generated misrepresentations, a persistent problem for Large Language Models, remains an unresolved quandary. While the OpenAI API was chosen for its simplicity and user-friendly interface, it is an expensive proprietary model. Adding support for alternative LLMs such as LLaMA or Alpaca could increase the flexibility and robustness of the entire system. Future work could also look at optimizing the vectorization of input geospatial data to reduce API costs and speed up inference. Data from OpenStreetMap also has limitations because it is not as sophisticated and generalized as the data crawled with Google Maps. Future developments could focus on incorporating more diverse and comprehensive data sources to improve the crawled geospatial data. In conclusion, this project successfully developed an integrated geospatial question-answering system using Large Language Models (LLMs), LangChain, ChromaDB, and modern front-end technologies. The system architecture includes a frontend built with React, Vite, and TailwindCSS, which uses the Mapbox JS library for an interactive map interface. The backend, built using

Python and Flask, handles data retrieval, processing, and interpretation. The system uses LLMs and LangChain to generate contextually appropriate responses to user queries. Geospatial data is pre-processed and transformed into embeddings stored in ChromaDB, enabling efficient query and retrieval of the crawled data. While the system demonstrates promising capabilities, it has limitations such as dependence on the quality of user input and the problem of hallucinations in LLMs. Future work could include incorporating alternative LLMs, optimizing data vectorization, and integrating more diverse data sources.

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